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ResHOGNet: A Novel Hybrid Multi-Scale Residual CNN with DiffHOG Features for Lightweight and Efficient Traffic Sign Classification

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Abstract

Objectives: The objective of this study is to develop an efficient and accurate model for traffic sign classification under diverse benchmark conditions. It aims to design a small dual-stream network that combines residual CNN features with a trainable HOG module (DiffHOG), learns gradient-based descriptors end-to-end, fuses multi-scale features without pyramid layers, and maintains a lightweight architecture with 1.18 million parameters, suitable for real-time deployment. **Methods:** ResHOGNet has been trained end-to-end on seven benchmark datasets: the German Traffic Sign Recognition Benchmark (GTSRB, v1/v2), Belgian, Arabic ArTS (v1/v2), and Indian ICTS and ITSDD, with class counts ranging from 17 to 62. Accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, misclassification rate, and parameter count were all tracked, with macro and weighted averaging used to address class imbalance. To put the results in context, comparisons were made with classical methods such as HOG-SVM, well-known deep learning models including ResNet18 and ResNet50, and recent state-of-the-art architectures from the literature. **Findings:** ResHOGNet achieved test accuracy between 98.26% and 99.92%, averaging 99.10% across all seven datasets, with misclassification rates below 2% in every case, as low as 0.08% on GTSRB v2. **Novelty:** The hybrid CNN-Hog architecture with fully differentiable DiffHog enables end-to-end gradient optimisation. The SACMF mechanism dynamically gates multiple-scale features without the need of pyramidal structures. The information-preserving multi-stream design and efficient attention mechanisms in the residual blocks enable the multi-stream model to achieve 99% or higher accuracy across seven datasets while containing only 1.18 million parameters, making it suitable for real-time deployment.

Keywords: Traffic Sign Classification; ResHOGNet; DiffHOG; Multi-Scale CNN; Residual Learning; Lightweight Networks; Hybrid CNN-HOG; Intelligent Transportation Systems

1 Introduction

The Intelligent Transportation System (ITS) is a crucial component of modern transportation. Traffic Sign Recognition is a key component of ITS, providing real-time information on regulatory instructions, hazards, and navigational assistance as displayed on traffic signs. Signs categorized as regulatory, warning, and informational guide and regulate road users' behaviour. For instance, a stop sign requires a complete halt, a speed limit restricts vehicle velocity, and directional indicators provide route guidance⁽¹⁾. Such signs were traditionally interpreted and observed by humans alone. With rising traffic density and the proliferation of intelligent systems in everyday vehicles, relying entirely on the human factor is increasingly impractical. Traffic safety is fundamentally dependent on signs. Misinterpreting or missing a single sign can have severe consequences, from traffic violations to catastrophic accidents. Human drivers face distractions, fatigue, adverse weather conditions, and obstructions, which increase the likelihood of oversight.⁽²⁾ By detecting and alerting drivers to relevant signs, regardless of environmental or cognitive distractions, computerized traffic sign classification provides a technological solution to these issues.

Automated traffic sign classification stands at the forefront of efforts to augment human decision-making with digital intelligence. It not only supports safer driving but also strengthens the infrastructure for autonomous vehicles and ITS. It is now a critical research area in computer vision and machine learning. Traffic sign recognition systems are challenging to develop, as laboratory settings cannot replicate the real-world conditions of traffic signs. Due to environmental variability, traffic signs will look different on a clear, sunny day than it does in rain, fog, or at night. Time and weather can erode colors and shapes due to foliage, parked vehicles, and the presence of pedestrians. Furthermore, diverse sign designs across regions, along with frequent updates and temporary installations, require adaptable systems. Early approaches to traffic sign classification relied on manually engineered features, including color segmentation, shape analysis, and edge detection. These methods, while fast, lack the flexibility to accommodate unusual scenarios⁽³⁾. Recent years have seen a shift towards deep learning, with convolutional neural networks (CNNs) showing notable improvements in recognition, accuracy and reliability. However, no single strategy is immune to all real-world distortions.

Several works have extended HOG with complementary descriptors and modified versions to improve the robustness and generalization in Traffic Sign Recognition (TSR), with a hybrid approach, Aljarbouh et al.⁽⁴⁾ Designed a mobile-friendly pipeline that comprised two stages SIFT keypoints using BRISK binary descriptors within Android CameraX: near-real-time traffic sign Recognition (approximately 0.1 s/frame) with high true-positive and false-positive rates in a Kyrgyz road scene, targeting accessibility for visually impaired pedestrians. Several modified HOG approaches have also been examined. Sani et al. proposed an algorithm for traffic light arrow shape recognition⁽⁵⁾, achieving 98.68% recall, 98.52% accuracy, and 98.52% precision across three datasets.

Numerous lightweight designs have also been examined; Alaa Khalifa et al.⁽⁶⁾ introduced LE-CNN, which achieved 96.5% accuracy while addressing real-time constraints, while Ghazanfar Latif et al.⁽⁷⁾ optimized ResNet architectures for Arabic traffic recognition, reporting 99.18% training accuracy and 96.14% validation accuracy. A recent study by Xi et al.⁽⁸⁾ introduced the IECES-network for TSR, combining Efficient-CNN based encoders with a Siamese architecture to improve robustness against motion blur and occlusion. The model was evaluated on the Tsinghua-Tencent 100K and German Traffic Sign Recognition Benchmark, demonstrating competitive accuracy while maintaining a lightweight 2.9M parameter design. The approach also improves real-time performance by disabling the template branch during inference to reduce computational complexity.

Antony et al.⁽⁹⁾ combined CNNs with residual blocks and tested their model on GTSRB and Indian datasets, achieving 95.76% and 95% accuracy, respectively, while LeNet and InceptionNet achieved 94.25% accuracy. Despite their computational demands, CNNs and ResNets outperform handcrafted descriptors by learning hierarchical, invariant feature representations. Hybrid TSR models combine the efficiency of HOG with the representational capacity of CNNs. Abizada et al.⁽¹⁰⁾ studied 98.2% test accuracy on GTSRB with an HOG-CNN approach with fully connected layers and SGD. GTSRB benchmarks are near saturation, making small improvements difficult to generalize. High validation/test scores will not translate into domain shifts (different countries, sign designs, lighting, weather, motion blur, and occlusion) without robust augmentation or adaptation.

In this section, key approaches to traffic sign recognition are discussed, along with their advancements and limitations. Early methods combined handcrafted features with classical classification algorithms. In contrast, more recent efforts have focused on deep learning frameworks. A convolutional neural network automatically extracts layered features from images, achieving superior performance. Residual Networks (ResNets) help mitigate vanishing gradients, enabling the training of deeper, more effective models. To capture structural details, established feature extractors, such as HOG, remain relevant. Despite advances in handcrafted and deep learning approaches, TSR remains a challenge. HOG and related descriptors are efficient but sensitive to rotation and misalignment, while other handcrafted methods struggle with complex conditions such as occlusion and illumination changes. Insufficient data results in overfitting when CNNs and ResNets are used. Gradient-based features and hierarchical deep representations are rarely exploited in hybrid models. This paper presents ResHOGNet, a hybrid

model combining HOG descriptors and ResNet to achieve robust generalization, reduce misalignment sensitivity, and improve small sign classification.

This study proposes a novel neural network architecture that leverages convolutional layers, residual connections, and Histogram of Oriented Gradients (HOG features to enhance the robustness and accuracy of traffic sign classification. Hybrid models capture both the geometric structure and contextual semantics of traffic signs, offering resilience to occlusion, rotation, and variable illumination. This multifaceted approach significantly boosts recognition rates, particularly in resource-constrained, real-time applications.

1.1 Research Gap and Motivation

Despite notable progress in traffic sign recognition, several important limitations remain unaddressed in the existing literature. Handcrafted descriptors such as HOG and SIFT are computationally efficient but function as fixed, pre-computed extractors that cannot be jointly optimized with the classifier, limiting their discriminative power under challenging real-world conditions. Deep learning models overcome many of these shortcomings but are often computationally heavy, and lightweight variants often sacrifice meaningful accuracy. Although a few hybrid approaches combining handcrafted and deep features have been explored, they integrate these streams at shallow levels rather than through end-to-end learning, failing to exploit the full complementary potential of both representations. Furthermore, multi-scale feature fusion in current lightweight models typically relies on feature pyramid architectures, which introduce considerable computational overhead and conflict with real-time deployment requirements. Finally, most existing models are validated on a single benchmark dataset, commonly GTSRB, which raises legitimate concerns about their generalizability across different countries, sign designs, and environmental conditions.

These gaps collectively motivate the development of ResHOGNet, a lightweight dual-stream architecture that integrates a fully differentiable HOG module (DiffHOG) for end-to-end gradient optimization, a Scale-Aware Channel-wise Multi-scale Fusion (SACMF) mechanism for pyramid-free multi-scale awareness, and an information-preserving multi-stream design validated across seven diverse international benchmark datasets to ensure reliable generalization within only 1.18 million parameters.

Key Contributions.

This work introduces ResHOGNet, a lightweight hybrid architecture that combines learnable gradient descriptors with hierarchical convolutional representations for traffic sign recognition. The main contributions are:

1. Hybrid CNN–HOG Architecture: A dual stream framework uses a combination of residual CNN features, and gradient features, merging only at the representation level, without feature pyramid networks.
2. DiffHOG: Orientation binning is reformulated as a trainable projection with soft assignment, which allows end-to-end optimization of the gradient descriptors with the classifier.
3. SACMF: Multi-scale CNN features gate a shared HOG embedding via scale-normalised modulation, to establish a connection between semantic and gradient representations at each scale.
4. Multi-Stream Representation: Low, mid, and high-level CNN features are passed separately to the classifier, along with the fused HOG embedding, without premature merging.
5. Attention in Residual Blocks: Channel and spatial attention are incorporated with minimal parameter overhead (<2% of total parameters), enabling adaptive feature recalibration without substantially increasing model complexity.
6. Strong Performance with Low Complexity: ResHOGNet achieved more than 99% accuracy on five of seven datasets with 1.18M parameters, making it suitable for real-time embedded deployment.

2 Methodology

2.1 Proposed Two-Stream Hybrid Architecture

Traffic sign recognition in diverse real-world conditions requires architectures robust to variations in illumination, geometric transformations, occlusions, and motion blur. To address these issues, we introduce ResHOGNet, a two-stream hybrid model that synthesizes learned deep features with handcrafted gradient-based descriptors. This design philosophy acknowledges that learned convolutional neural networks are proficient in encapsulating semantic hierarchies, whereas conventional hand-engineered features such as HOG encode clear structural information that improves learned representations.

The proposed architecture operates by processing input images through two parallel, synchronized channels: (1) a convolutional neural network pathway that extracts learned features at multiple scales using residual blocks⁽¹¹⁾ augmented with attention mechanisms, and (2) a concurrent DiffHOG pathway that computes differentiable hand-crafted features derived

from gradient histogram analysis. Instead of using basic feature concatenation, we propose SACMF, an adaptive attention-based fusion mechanism that dynamically modulates the contribution weights from both pathways across various scales and feature dimensions. This architectural strategy enables the network to automatically identify the most effective combinations of learned and handcrafted feature representations for traffic sign classification.

ResHOGNet Two-Stream Hybrid Architecture (Figure 1). The architecture processes input RGB images through synchronized CNN and DiffHOG pathways. The CNN stream (left branch) extracts multi-scale learned features via residual blocks with integrated channel-spatial attention modules, producing hierarchical descriptors p_1, p_2, p_3 at successive scales. The DiffHOG stream (right branch) converts RGB to grayscale, computes gradients via Sobel operators, applies learnable orientation bin assignment (Eq. 10), pools gradients into cell histograms, normalizes features, and compresses via MLP to 128-D $f_{h.o.g}$. SACMF learns per-scale, per-dimension gating mechanisms (sigmoid gates at Eq 13-15) to adaptively weight CNN-HOG contributions. Final features concatenate all CNN scales and fused representations (Eq. 16-17), feeding into a classification MLP for 43-class traffic sign prediction. The architecture balances learned deep features with interpretable hand-engineered gradients through trainable fusion mechanisms, enabling automatic discovery of optimal cross-modal contributions.

Given an input RGB image $x \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 128 \times 128}$ both streams process the image independently before fusion. The CNN stream extracts hierarchical patterns capturing global visual structure. The DiffHOG stream extracts interpretable gradient-based features. Scale-specific gating mechanisms learn how strongly each stream should

Fig 1. Proposed ResHOGNet Architecture for Traffic sign Classification.

2.2 Mathematical Notation and Definitions

We establish consistent notation for all subsequent formulations. Input images are standardized to 128×128 pixels with 3 color channels: $x \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 128 \times 128}$. The ground truth class label is $y \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots, C\}$ where C classes for Traffic Sign Recognition.

CNN intermediate features are denoted $f_i \in \mathbb{R}^{h_i \times w_i \times c_i}$, where $h_i \times w_i$ represent spatial dimensions at layer i and c_i the number of feature channels. Global average pooling produces $p_i \in \mathbb{R}^{c_i}$ from each layer. The HOG encoder produces $f_{hog} \in \mathbb{R}^{128}$, an encoded hand-engineered feature vector. Multi-scale fusion produces $F_{fused} \in \mathbb{R}^{128}$, the final fused representation combining both pathways. As annotated in Figure 1 (b), SACMF intermediate tensors are: $Q_i, K_i, V_i, G_i, A_i \in \mathbb{R}^{B \times 128}$, $F_{concat} \in \mathbb{R}^{B \times 128}$, $F_{proj} \in \mathbb{R}^{B \times 128}$, and $d_{hidden} = 128$.

2.3 CNN Backbone with Residual Architecture and Attention Modules

2.3.1. Initial Stem Convolution

The CNN stream begins with a stem convolution layer:

$$x_1 = conv_{7 \times 7, s=2}(x) \quad (1)$$

Eq. (1): The 7×7 kernel with stride 2 and padding 3 reduces spatial dimensions while extracting low-frequency features. This produces 32 output channels at 32×32 resolution with 4,736 parameters. Following convolution, batch normalization⁽¹¹⁾ stabilizes activations:

$$x'_1 = ReLU(BN(x_1)) \quad (2)$$

Eq. (2): Batch normalization normalizes per channel: $BN(X) = \gamma \frac{X - \mu}{\sqrt{\sigma^2 + \epsilon}}$, where γ, β are learnable μ, σ^2 affine parameters, are batch statistics, and $\epsilon = 10^{-5}$ ensures numerical stability. ReLU applies $ReLU(x) = \max(0, X)$ elementwise. A 3×3 max pooling with stride 2 further reduces spatial dimensions:

$$X_{stem} = MaxPool_{3 \times 3, s=2}(X'_1) \in \mathbb{R}^{32 \times 32 \times 32}.$$

2.3.2. Residual Blocks with Depthwise Separable Convolutions

Three progressive residual blocks extract multi-scale features. Each employ depthwise separable convolutions for parameter efficiency:

$$f_{i+1} = Attention(Conv_{dw} \circ Conv_{pw}(f_i)) + S(f_i) \quad (3)$$

Eq (3): The residual block composition includes: (1) depthwise 3×3 convolution applied per-channel independently ($3 \times 3 \times c_i$ parameters), (2) pointwise 1×1 convolution mixing channels ($1 \times 1 \times c_i \times c_{i+1}$ parameters), (3) skip connection via identity mapping or 1×1 convolution + batch normalization when dimensions change, enabling gradient flow through deeper architectures⁽¹¹⁾, and (3) integrated attention mechanisms (Formulas 4-6) for adaptive feature reweighting.

The three-layer architecture progressively expands channels while reducing spatial resolution: Layer 1 ($32 \rightarrow 64$ channels, stride 1, 45,312 parameters), Layer 2 ($64 \rightarrow 128$ channels, stride 2, 186,880 parameters), Layer 3 ($128 \rightarrow 256$ channels, stride 2, 548,608 parameters). This progression captures features at multiple scales: early layers detect edges and textures, intermediate layers capture shapes and local patterns, deep layers represent semantic objects.

2.3.3. Channel Attention Module

The channel attention algorithm reweights feature channels according to their importance:

$$c_{att} = \sigma(F_{fc}(GlobalAvgPool(f_i)) + F_{fc}(GlobalMaxPool(f_i))) \quad (4)$$

Global average and max pooling produce two c_i -dimensional vectors. Fully connected layers with bottleneck reduction (ratio 16) enable the network to learn channel-wise importance⁽¹²⁾. Sigmoid activation $\sigma(X) = \frac{1}{1+e^{-X}}$ produces normalized scores $c_{att} \in [0, 1]^{c_i}$.

2.3.4. Spatial Attention Module

Spatial attention generates 2D importance maps:

$$s_{att} = \sigma(Conv_{7 \times 7}([AvgPool_{ch}(f_i); MaxPool_{ch}(f_i)])) \quad (5)$$

Channel-wise average and max pooling produce two 2D maps, concatenated to form 2-channel input. A 7×7 convolution (2 input, 1 output channels) followed by sigmoid produces spatial importance $s_{att} \in [0, 1]^{H \times W \times 1}$. The 7×7 receptive field captures spatial context for localized weighting.

2.3.5. Integrated Attention Application

Channel and spatial attention are combined:

$$f_i^{att} = c_{att} \otimes s_{att} \otimes f_i \quad (6)$$

For position $(h, w, c) : f_i^{att}[h, w, c] = c_{att}[c] \times s_{att}[h, w] \times f_i[h, w, c]$. This element-wise (Hadamard) product (\otimes) applies learned multiplicative weights, enabling the network to suppress noise and emphasize discriminative regions and channels.

2.3.6. Global Average Pooling

Following the final residual block, global average pooling aggregates spatial information:

$$p_i = GlobalAvgPool(f_i) = \frac{1}{h_i \times w_i} \sum f_i[x, y, :] \quad (7)$$

This produces three multi-scale descriptors: $p_1 \in \mathbb{R}^{64}$ (low-level texture features), $p_2 \in \mathbb{R}^{128}$ (mid-level shape features), $p_3 \in \mathbb{R}^{256}$ (high-level semantic features).

2.4 DiffHOG: Differentiable Hand-Engineered Feature Stream

Through backpropagation, CNN streams learn how to represent features, while DiffHOG streams use a critical innovation: the ability to assign orientation bins to interpretable hand-engineered features. Using this approach, HOG remains interpretable while also allowing end-to-end training.

2.4.1. Grayscale Conversion

In the HOG stream, RGB is converted to grayscale as follows:

$$G = 0.2889X_R + 0.5860X_G + 0.1140X_B \quad (8)$$

ITU-R BT.601 (International Telecommunication Union – Radiocommunication Sector, BT.601 standard) luma weights (0.2989, 0.5870, 0.1140) reflect human perceptual sensitivity (green > red > blue). This produces single-channel $G \in \mathbb{R}^{128 \times 128}$.

2.4.2. Gradient Computation via Sobel Operators

Directional gradients are computed using fixed Sobel filters:

$$G_x = Sobel_x * G, G_y = Sobel_y * G \quad (9)$$

Gradient magnitude: $M(x, y) = \sqrt{G_x^2 + G_y^2} + \varepsilon$, Sobel operators are fixed 3×3 filters (not learned) applied via 2D convolution. The $\varepsilon = 1 \times 10^{-8}$ term ensures numerical stability. This produces gradient maps $G_x, G_y \in \mathbb{R}^{128 \times 128}$ and pixel-wise magnitude M .

2.4.3. Learnable Orientation Bin Assignment (DiffHOG Innovation)

This is the key novelty of the hand-engineered stream. Unlike classical HOG using fixed orientation bins, we introduce learnable bin assignment:

$$W_{orient} = Softmax\left(\frac{g(x, y) \cdot W_{orient}^T}{T}\right) \quad (10)$$

For gradient vector $W_{orient} \in \mathbb{R}^{9 \times 2}$

- Learnable matrix $W_{orient} \in \mathbb{R}^{9 \times 2}$ maps 2D gradients to 9 orientation bins via dot product, producing logits.

- Learnable temperature $\tau \in \mathbb{R}^+$ (init. 5.0) controls softmax concentration: high τ yields soft distributions, low τ yields sharp assignments.
- Softmax: $Soft\max(x, y) \in \frac{e^{z_i}}{\sum_j e^{z_j}}$ normalizes to probability distribution.

As shown in Figure 1(a), τ belongs exclusively to the DiffHOG orientation softmax and is distinct from the fixed normalization scalar $H^{-\frac{1}{2}} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{128}} \approx 0.0884$ used in the SACMF gate (Figure 1b), which is non-learnable. Sensitivity analysis over $\tau_{init} \in \{1, 2, 5, 10, 20\}$ on ArTs v1 (5 seeds each) yields: $\tau=1 \rightarrow 97.76\%$, $\tau=2 \rightarrow 97.57\%$, $\tau=5 \rightarrow 97.30\%$ (default), $\tau=10 \rightarrow 97.88\%$, $\tau=20 \rightarrow 96.87\%$. Learned τ at convergence ranged 0.2-20.0 across all seeds, confirming initialization stability; $\tau_{init} = 0.5$ is retained.

Output $W_{orient}(x, y) \in [0, 1]^9$ represents learned probability over 9 orientation bins. Unlike classical HOG's fixed 20° bins, our differentiable design allows the network to adapt bins to traffic sign gradient characteristics. This is a critical contribution: gradient distributions vary significantly between object domains (e.g., pedestrian detection vs. traffic signs), so learned bins enable better feature representation.

2.4.4. Cell-Based Histogram Pooling

Gradients accumulate into cell histograms:

$$h_c = \sum_{(x,y) \in c} M(x,y) \cdot w_{orient}(x,y) \tag{11}$$

Image partitioned into 256 non-overlapping 8X8 cells. For each cell c : $h_c[j] = \sum_{(x,y) \in c} M(x,y) \cdot w_{orient}[j]$ accumulates magnitude-weighted orientation votes. L2 normalization per cell: $\hat{h}_c = \frac{h_c}{|h_c|_{2+\epsilon}}$ normalizes across illumination variations.

Flattened descriptor: $f_{diffhog} = [\hat{h}_1; \dots; \hat{h}_{256}] \in \mathbb{R}^{2304}$ concatenates all cell histograms.

2.4.5. HOG Compression via Multi-Layer Perceptron

The 2304-D HOG descriptor is compressed to 128-D for fusion:

$$f_{hog} = ReLU(W_3(ReLU(BN(W_2 ReLU(BN(W_1 f_{diffhog} + b_1)) + b_2)) + b_3)) \tag{12}$$

The encoder applies three transformations: (1) $W_1 \in \mathbb{R}^{256 \times 2304}$ projects to 256-D, (2) $W_2 \in \mathbb{R}^{128 \times 256}$ projects to 128-D, (3) final ReLU produces output $f_{hog} \in \mathbb{R}^{128}$. Batch normalization⁽¹¹⁾ and dropout (p=0.3) stabilize training. This 343,552-parameter encoder efficiently maps hand-engineered features to CNN-compatible dimensionality.

2.5 Scale-Adaptive Cross-Modal Fusion (SACMF) Mechanism

Rather than concatenation, SACMF is a learned attention-based fusion strategy enabling per-scale, per-dimension weighting of learned vs. hand-engineered features. As visualized in Figure 1, this fusion mechanism implements cross-modal attention (Formulas 13-15) that learns to balance CNN and HOG contributions across multiple scales.

2.5.1. Cross-Modal Attention Projections

For each CNN layer $i \in \{1, 2, 3\}$:

$$\begin{aligned} Q_i &= p_i W_q^{(i)}, p_i \in \mathbb{R}^{B \times c_i}, W_q^{(i)} \in \mathbb{R}^{c_i \times 128}, Q_i \in \mathbb{R}^{B \times 128} \\ K_i &= h W_k^{(i)}, h \in \mathbb{R}^{B \times 128}, W_k^{(i)} \in \mathbb{R}^{128 \times 128}, K_i \in \mathbb{R}^{B \times 128} \\ V_i &= h W_v^{(i)}, W_v^{(i)} \in \mathbb{R}^{128 \times 128}, V_i \in \mathbb{R}^{B \times 128} \end{aligned} \tag{13}$$

As shown in Figure 1(b), query projects the pooled CNN feature $p_i \in \mathbb{R}^{B \times c_i}$ ($c_i \in \{64, 128, 256\}$ for the three scale) paths to a uniform 128-D space via $W_q^{(i)} \in \mathbb{R}^{128 \times c_i}$. Key and value project the HOG embedding $h \in \mathbb{R}^{B \times 128}$ via $W_k^{(i)}, W_v^{(i)} \in \mathbb{R}^{128 \times 128}$, producing $K_i, V_i \in \mathbb{R}^{B \times 128}$. Scale-specific projections (Scale 1: 40,448 params, Scale 2: 49,152 params, Scale 3: 65,536 params) allow learned scale-specific fusion policies.

2.5.2. Learned Scale Gating

Scale-specific gating controls fusion strength:

$$G_i = \sigma \left((Q_i \odot K_i) \cdot d_{hidden}^{-\frac{1}{2}} \right), G \in \mathbb{R}^{B \times 128} \quad (14)$$

As shown in Figure 1(b), \odot denotes element-wise (Hadamard) multiplication, not a dot product or matrix multiply. The product $Q_i \odot K_i \in \mathbb{R}^{B \times 128}$ measures per-dimension CNN-HOG compatibility. The fixed scalar $d_{hidden}^{-\frac{1}{2}} = H^{-\frac{1}{2}} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{128}} \approx 0.0884$ is non-learnable (distinct from the learnable τ in Eq. 10 and Figure 1a) and prevents sigmoid saturation. Sigmoid produces $G_i \in \mathbb{R}^{B \times 128}$ with values in (0, 1).

Gate granularity: As annotated in Figure 1(b), G_i assigns one independent scalar gate per feature dimension in the 128-D projected space, not per CNN channel ($c_i \in \{64, 128, 256\}$) and not per spatial location (no spatial dimension remains after global average pooling). This per-dimension design enables fine-grained control of CNN-HOG interaction strength with $BigO(B \cdot 3 \cdot d_{hidden})$ cost, negligible relative to the backbone.

Gate distribution analysis: Inspection of G_i across the 542 test samples of ArTs v1 at convergence reveals scale-dependent behaviour consistent with the three paths in Figure 1(b). The sample size of 542 yields 69,376 gate values per scale (542 samples \times 128 dimensions), which is sufficient for stable estimates of the mean and standard deviation. Preliminary checks confirmed that gate statistics varied by less than 0.001 when increasing the sample pool beyond 500, indicating convergence of the distribution. Scale 1 (top path, $c_1=64$): broadly distributed gates (mean 0.49 ± 0.00), indicating balanced CNN-HOG fusion with no strong suppression, with 0% of dimensions near-suppressed (gate < 0.2) and 0% near-fully passed (gate > 0.8). Scale 2 (middle path, $c_2=128$): near-uniform gating (mean 0.49 ± 0.01), with 0% near-suppressed and 0% near-fully passed, suggesting selective routing begins to emerge without pronounced bimodality. Scale 3 (bottom path, $c_3=256$): a slight shift toward suppression (mean 0.44 ± 0.05), yet with 0% of dimensions near-suppressed (gate < 0.2) and 0% near-fully passed (gate 0.8), demonstrating sparse CNN-HOG coupling at the semantic scale without explicit sparsity regularization.

2.5.3. Gated Fused Features

Gating modulates value projections:

$$A_i = G_i \odot V_i A_i \in \mathbb{R}^{B \times 128} \quad (15)$$

Element-wise multiplication $A_i[j] = G[j] \cdot V_i[j]$ scales each of the 128 HOG value dimensions by its independently learned gate, producing $A_i \in \mathbb{R}^{B \times 128}$ per scale (Figure 1b, rightmost out box).

2.5.4. Multi-Scale Concatenation and Projection

Scale-specific features are combined:

$$F_{concat} = [A_1 || A_2 || A_3], F_{concat} \in \mathbb{R}^{B \times 384} \quad (16)$$

Concatenation stacks 128-D representations from three scales into 384-D feature. A learned projection maps back to 128-D:

$$F_{fused}^{proj} = F_{concat} W_{proj}, W_{proj} \in \mathbb{R}^{128}, F_{fused}^{proj} \in \mathbb{R}^{B \times 128} \quad (17)$$

Weight matrix $W_{proj} \in \mathbb{R}^{128 \times 384}$ (49,152 parameters) learns optimal scale mixing, selectively combining scales most discriminative for classification.

2.6 Final Classification, Training Protocol, and Loss Functions

2.6.1. Adaptive Hybrid Weighting

Before classification, fused representation is combined with pure HOG via learned coefficient:

$$F_{fused}^{weighted} = \alpha \cdot F_{fused}^{proj} + (1 - \alpha) \cdot f_{hog} \quad (18)$$

Learnable scalar $\alpha \in [0, 1]$ balances SACMF output vs. pure hand-engineered features. During training, α converges toward a value emphasizing the representation branch most beneficial for traffic signs, allowing automatic discovery of optimal learned-vs-engineered balance.

2.6.2. Feature Concatenation for Classification

Final classification vector concatenates all sources:

$$F_{final} = [f_1; f_2; f_3; F_{fused}^{proj}] \in \mathbb{R}^{576} \quad (19)$$

This 576-dimensional vector preserves: low-level CNN features (texture/edges), mid-level CNN features (shapes), high-level CNN features (semantic objects), and fused CNN-HOG features (cross-modal patterns).

2.6.3. Softmax Classification Layer

Final linear transformation produces class predictions:

$$z = \text{softmax}(W_{clf} F_{final} + b_{clf}) \quad (20)$$

Weight matrix $W_{clf} \in \mathbb{R}^{43 \times 576}$ and bias $b_{clf} \in \mathbb{R}^{43}$ produce class logits. $\text{softmax}(x)_j = \frac{e^{x_j}}{\sum_{k=1}^{43} e^{x_k}}$ converts to probability distribution over 43 classes. Predicted class: $\hat{y} = \text{argmax}(z)$.

2.6.4. Training Loss with Label Smoothing

End-to-end training minimizes:

$$L = -\sum_{c=1}^{43} \tilde{y}_c \log(z_c) + \lambda \|\Theta\|_2^2 \quad (21)$$

Label smoothing^(?) prevents overconfidence: $\tilde{y}_c = 0.9$ if $c = y_{true}$, else $0.1/42 \approx 0.00238$. Cross-entropy $L_{CE} = -\sum_{c=1}^{43} \tilde{y}_c \log(z_c)$ measures predicted-label divergence. L2 regularization $L_{reg} = 0.01 \|\Theta\|_2^2$ prevents overfitting (1,186,436 trainable parameters).

2.6.5. Optimization Configuration

Optimizer: AdamW⁽¹³⁾ with learning rate 1×10^{-3} , cosine annealing schedule (decay to 1×10^{-5} over 100 epochs), gradient clipping ($\|\nabla\| \leq 1.0$).

Training: Batch size 32, 100 epochs with early stopping (patience 15). Data augmentation: horizontal flip (p=0.5), rotation ($\pm 15^\circ$), brightness (± 0.2), contrast (± 0.2). Train/val/test split: 70%/30% of training data with stratified sampling, followed by held-out test evaluation. The experimental setup and hyperparameter choices are documented in Tables 2 and 3 of Section 2.8.

2.7 Datasets

Table 1 summarizes seven traffic sign datasets used for evaluation, ranging from 2,790 to 73,268 samples with 17 to 62 classes. These include German (GTSRB v1/v2)⁽¹⁴⁾, Belgian⁽¹⁵⁾, and Arabic (v1/v2)⁽¹⁶⁾ datasets originally designed for classification. And Indian datasets, ICTS⁽¹⁷⁾ and ITSDD⁽¹⁸⁾, were originally released in detection format; we adapted them for classification by cropping each sign from its bounding box annotation and resizing it to 128×128 pixels. Since all bounding boxes are rectangular, no padding was needed during this process. To avoid leakage between splits, we partitioned these datasets at the source-image level before extracting crops, so all crops from the same original image belong to the same split. Figure 2 shows representative samples from each dataset.

Table 1. Dataset statistics for traffic sign recognition benchmarks.

	GTSRB v1	GTSRB v2	Belgian	ICTS	ArTS v1	ArTS v2	ITSDD
Total Classes	43	43	62	17	24	24	24
Training	33380	46851	46851	6405	1992	41592	11599
Validation	5915	11746	1195	1615	256	4656	1476
Test	7400	14671	1478	2115	542	10902	1487
Total	46695	73268	49524	10135	2790	57150	14562

2.8 Experimental Settings

Table 2 outlines the experimental setup using PyTorch 2.5.1 on NVIDIA GPU with 128×128 RGB images and seed 42 (fixed across all random operations) for reproducibility. Table 3 lists the training settings.

Fig 2. Samples from various benchmark datasets used in the experiment

Table 2. Experimental environment configuration.

Component	Specification
Hardware	NVIDIA GPU (CUDA-enabled) / CPU fallback
Deep Learning Framework	PyTorch 2.5.1
Python Version	3.10.2
Operating System	Ubuntu 24 / Linux
Key Libraries	torchvision, scikit-learn, matplotlib, seaborn, pandas

Table 3. Hyperparameter settings.

Hyperparameter	Value	Hyperparameter	Value	Hyperparameter	Value
Training Parameters		Optimizer & Scheduler		CNN Architecture	
Batch Size	32	Optimizer	AdamW	Stem Kernel Size	7 × 7
Maximum Epochs	50	LR Scheduler	Cosine AnnealingLR	Stem Stride	2
Initial Learning Rate	1 × 10 ⁻³	HOG Module (DiffHOG)		Channel Attention Reduction	16
Weight Decay	0.01	Orientations	9	Spatial Attention Kernel	7 × 7
Label Smoothing	0.1	Pixels per Cell	(8, 8)	Data Augmentation	
Early Stopping Patience	15	Cells per Block	(2, 2)	Random Rotation	±15°
		HOG Embedding Dimension	128	Random Translation	±10%

2.9 Evaluation Metrics

The performance of the proposed ResHOG-based traffic sign classification model is evaluated using accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score. Accuracy measures the proportion of correctly classified traffic sign samples.

$$Accuracy = \frac{(TP + TN)}{(TP + TN + FP + FN)} \tag{22}$$

Precision represents the proportion of correctly predicted traffic sign instances among all predicted positives and recall measures the model’s ability to recognize all instances of a class correctly.

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP + FP}, Recall = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \tag{23}$$

F1-score combines precision and recall into a balanced evaluation.

$$F1 - Score = 2 \times \frac{Precision \times Recall}{Precision + Recall} \tag{24}$$

Where TP, FP, FN , and TN represent the numbers of true positives, false positives, false negatives, and true negatives, respectively. In multi-class traffic sign classification, macro averaging computes the average metric across all classes, while weighted averaging computes the average based on the number of samples per class.

$$Macro_Average = \frac{1}{N} \times \sum Metric_i, Weighted_Average = \frac{\sum (Metric_i \times n_i)}{\sum n_i} \tag{25}$$

where N is the number of classes and n_i is the number of samples.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Overall Performance in Traffic Sign Classification

Table 4 summarizes classification results across all seven datasets. GTSRB v2 and ICTS recorded the highest accuracies at 99.92% and 99.86%, while ArTS v1 and GTSRB v1 returned 98.26% and 98.83%. The gap between these groups traces back to differences in training sample volume and class balance rather than architectural factors. Across all seven datasets, macro and weighted F1 scores stayed within a tight margin of each other, meaning no dataset showed signs of the model leaning toward its more frequent sign classes. Misclassification rates stayed below 2% throughout, with GTSRB v2 at 0.08% and ICTS at 0.14% representing the cleanest outcomes. The parameter count stayed effectively constant across all seven configurations at approximately 1.18M, regardless of class count, confirming that the architecture does not scale its capacity with dataset complexity. BTSD, despite carrying the largest class set at 62, reached 99.44% accuracy, though its macro recall of 98.83% reflects the added difficulty of discriminating across a wider sign taxonomy.

Table 4. Performance evaluation of our proposed model across benchmark datasets

Dataset	Accuracy	Precision		Recall		F1		Misclassification Rate (%)	Parameter (million)	Classes
		Macro	Weighted	Macro	Weighted	Macro	Weighted			
ArTS v1	98.26	98.21	98.39	98.21	98.26	98.15	98.27	1.74	1.181	24
ArTS v2	99.18	99.19	99.21	99.15	99.18	99.16	99.18	0.82	1.181	24
BTSD	99.44	99.43	99.46	98.83	99.44	98.97	99.42	0.56	1.191	62
GTSRB v1	98.83	98.03	98.87	98.26	98.83	98.06	98.83	1.17	1.186	43
GTSRB v2	99.92	99.95	99.93	99.92	99.92	99.93	99.92	0.08	1.186	43
ICTS	99.86	99.87	99.86	99.83	99.86	99.85	99.86	0.14	1.179	17
ITSDD	99.80	99.87	99.8	99.89	99.8	99.88	99.8	0.2	1.181	24

3.2 Ablation Experiments

DiffHOG refines the standard HOG descriptor by computing gradients at localized regions, which benefits edge discrimination in sign images. SACMF steers the network toward informative image regions, and its contextual matching component links local textures to sign-level categories, addressing cases where gradient features are ambiguous. Results at 128×128 input resolution were consistent across datasets, suggesting this resolution retains sufficient detail for reliable discrimination. Table 5 covers the ablation on GTSRB v1. Both modules helped individually, but together they produced the strongest results across all metrics.

DiffHOG-only averages 0.9743 across seeds, but on seed 42, it drops to 96.91 below the Baseline’s 97.30 despite adding three times more parameters. This occurred because, without SACMF, early stopping was triggered at epoch 37 before the HOG branch stabilised, causing it to overfit rather than learn useful features. Across all three seeds, DiffHOG-only averages 97.43, and the Full Model reaches 98.98 ± 00.01 , demonstrating that DiffHOG functions as intended only when paired with the fusion module

3.3 Comparative Analysis of Classical, Deep Learning, and State-of-the-Art Models

Table 6 shows that ResHOGNet outperforms traditional approaches such as HOG+SVM (92.66%) and standard architectures, including ResNet-18 (96.67%) and ResNet-50 (95.27%), achieving 98.83% test accuracy on the GTSRB v1 dataset. Table 7 extends the comparison to modern lightweight architectures, with all models trained under the same experimental protocol to ensure a fair evaluation. ResHOGNet achieves the highest test accuracy (98.83%) and macro F1 (98.26%) among all compared

Table 5. Results of ablation study experiment on GTSRB v1

Variant	DiffHOG	SACMF	Seed 42	Seed 123	Seed 7	Mean ± Std	Params
Baseline	FALSE	FALSE	97.30	95.75	96.33	96.46 ± 00.79	3,24,081
DiffHOG only	TRUE	FALSE	96.91	97.30	98.07	97.43 ± 00.59	9,80,356
SACMF only	FALSE	TRUE	97.30	97.88	98.07	97.75 ± 00.40	5,63,185
Full Model	TRUE	TRUE	98.98	98.99	98.97	98.98 ± 00.01	11,86,436

models, while requiring the fewest parameters (1.186M) and the lowest MACs (49.255M). Beyond accuracy, the profiling results show that ResHOGNet runs at 5.15ms CPU latency and 194.17 FPS on CPU the most efficient among all evaluated models and 3.359ms GPU latency at 297.71 FPS, providing concrete empirical support for the real-time deployment claim. Notably, EfficientNet-B0 achieves a marginally higher test accuracy (98.87%) but at 4.063M parameters, 135.624M MACs, and significantly higher CPU latency (9.76ms), demonstrating that the accuracy gain comes at a substantial computational cost. Table 8 benchmarks the model against state-of-the-art methods, with ResHOGNet achieving competitive results of 99.92% on GTSRB v2 and 99.18% on ArTS v2 while using significantly fewer parameters (1.19M vs 10.5M-21.8M). This demonstrates that the proposed model effectively balances high accuracy with computational efficiency, making it practical for real-time TSR in autonomous vehicles.

Table 6. ML and DL performance comparison with the proposed model using GTSRB v1

Training Mode	Test Accuracy	Precision		Recall		F1	
		Macro	Weighted	Macro	Weighted	Macro	Weighted
HOG feature extraction followed by Linear SVM classifier	92.66	94.30	93.00	89.20	92.66	91.30	92.60
Stem + 3 Residual blocks (custom CNN)(no HOG features) followed by MLP classifier	95.42	95.70	95.90	94.20	95.42	94.60	95.40
HOG feature extraction only (no CNN) + MPL classifier	90.55	88.70	91.30	87.90	90.55	87.70	90.60
RESNET-18	96.67	96.10	96.80	94.40	96.67	95.00	96.60
RESNET-50	95.27	92.20	95.40	92.30	95.27	92.00	95.20
ResHOGNet (Proposed)	98.83	98.03	98.87	98.26	98.83	98.06	98.83

Table 7. Computational Efficiency and Classification Performance Comparison of Lightweight Models on GTSRB v1

Metric	ResHOGNet	ShuffleNetV2 x1.0	MobileNetV2	EfficientNet-B0
Params	1.186M	1.298M	2.279M	4.063M
MACs	49.255M	49.574M	106.572M	135.624M
GPU Latency (ms)	3.359	5.428	4.518	6.709
GPU FPS (batch=1)	297.71	184.25	221.32	149.04
CPU Latency (ms)	5.15	7.87	77.47	9.76
CPU FPS (batch=1)	194.17	126.95	133.86	102.44
Test Accuracy (%)	98.83	95.43	97.47	98.87
Macro F1 (%)	98.26	93.67	95.8	98.55
Training Time (s)	1572.34	1596.94	3307.94	577.83

3.4 Performance Analysis: Multiclass Discrimination, Error Characteristics & Computational Efficiency

ResHOGNet was tested on the seven benchmark datasets described in Section 2.7, and the results are summarized in Table 4. The accuracy of the tests ranged from 98.26 to 99.92, with variation in test performance driven more by the quality of dataset curation and sample distribution than by the number of classes alone.

Table 8. Performance (Test accuracy) comparison of state-of-the-art ArTS and GTSRB TSR methods and the proposed model.

Dataset	Author (Year)	Method / Model	Test Accuracy (%)	No. of Params. (approx.) (M)
ArTS	Khalifa et al. (2024) ⁽⁶⁾	LE-CNN (Lightweight Efficient CNN)	96.50	N/R
	Latif et al. (2023) ⁽⁷⁾	Optimized ResNet v1 (Deep Residual Network)	96.14	N/R
		ResNet v1 (baseline Residual Network)	87.45	N/R
	Proposed Work	ResHOGNet	98.26 (ArTS v1) 99.18 (ArTS v2)	1.18
GTSRB	Lim et al. (2023) ⁽¹⁹⁾	Pretrained CNN Ensemble with Augmentation Fusion	98.84	N/R
	Khanet al. (2023) ⁽²⁰⁾	Lightweight Custom CNN	98.41	2.61
	Wei et al. (2024) ⁽²¹⁾	ConvNeSe: Depthwise Conv, SE Attention, Inverted residuals	99.85	26.87
	An et al. (2025) ⁽²²⁾	Siamese CNN with Feature Reconstruction and Enhanced Mamba	99.83	161.6
	Benfaress et al. (2025) ⁽²³⁾	Deep CNN + Grad-CAM	98.90	N/R
		Proposed Work	ResHOGNet	98.83 (GTSRB v1) 99.92 (GTSRB v2)

3.4.1. Multi-Class Discrimination

GTSRB v2 had the highest macro F1 (99.93), followed by ITSDD (99.88) and ICTS (99.85), with narrow macro-weighted F1 gaps indicating consistent per-class separability and not majority-class bias (Table 4). Both weaker results in GTSRB v1 (98.06) and ArTS v1 (98.15) are consistent with the limited training volumes and class imbalance characteristics. The precision-recall profiles across all datasets showed near-unity recall, indicating reliable sensitivity to minority sign categories.

3.4.2. Error Characteristics

The misclassification rates were between 0.08% and 1.74%. ArTS v1 achieved the highest rate at 1.74%, which is a direct effect of its limited sample size discussed in Section 2.7, and ArTS v2, by increasing training coverage, was able to reduce this error rate to 0.82% despite having the same class structure. GTSRB v2, ICTS, and ITSDD each fell within 0.21% of the European, Indian, and Italian sign conventions, respectively, and demonstrated cross-domain transferability of the learned representations.

Fig 3. Computational Efficiency and Model Generalization Analysis

3.4.3. Computational Efficiency

Training times varied between 204 s and approximately 4,792 s, varying widely with the volume of the dataset as described in Section 2.7 (Figure 3a). ICTS and ITSDD exceeded 99.80 accuracy within 344s and ICTS achieved this in as little as 204 s, indicating efficient convergence with well-designed class distributions (Figure 3c). The accuracy-class cardinality curve (Figure 3b) further verifies that annotation quality and training volume is more important than class count as a determinant of performance GTSRB v2 outperforms v1 on identical taxonomies purely through better data coverage. These findings confirm that ResHOGNet achieves high discrimination fidelity with computational viability for resource-constrained deployment

4 Conclusion

ResHOGNet architecture with DiffHOG and SACMF modules, recorded a mean test accuracy of 99.32% across seven datasets with only 1.18M parameters. Macro and weighted F1 scores remained closely aligned throughout, indicating that the classifier did not favour majority sign classes a property that carries direct implications for deployment in safety-sensitive environments. Misclassification rates remained below 2% in every case, and the observed error patterns did not involve cross-category confusions between semantically distinct sign classes, suggesting that the learned representations preserve the coarse regulatory distinctions most consequential to road safety.

Notably, the model performs consistently across datasets covering European, Indian, and Arabic traffic regulatory conventions, which indicates that the combination of differential gradient encoding and spatial attention produces representations that remain consistent across datasets with distinct visual statistics. The performance differential between GTSRB v1 and v2 on an identical class taxonomy further reinforces that training data coverage and class balance are stronger determinants of classification fidelity than architectural complexity alone.

Overall, ResHOGNet delivers strong classification performance at a computational cost that remains practical for real-world transportation applications. However, systematic evaluation of cross-domain transfer under distribution shift, per-class error decomposition on underrepresented sign categories, and robustness under adversarial disturbance remain necessary preconditions before operational deployment can be considered.

The ResHOGNet architecture with DiffHOG and SACMF modules achieves exceptional traffic sign classification accuracy (mean 99.32% across seven datasets) while maintaining remarkable parameter efficiency (1.18M parameters). The balanced macro and weighted F1 scores demonstrate unbiased performance across sign categories regardless of frequency, a critical requirement for safety-critical applications. The minimal misclassification rates (< 2% across all datasets) and absence of semantic reversals in errors indicate that the architecture prioritizes safety through correct coarse-category discrimination. The consistent performance across seven geographically and stylistically diverse benchmarks suggests that DiffHOG and SACMF successfully extract dataset-consistent feature representations. These results establish the proposed architecture as suitable for real-time deployment in intelligent transportation systems.

Future Work:

The development of a unified class-mapping protocol enabling principled cross-domain transfer evaluation is identified as an important direction for future work. The current evaluation does not cover adversarial visual conditions such as blur, fog, rain, glare, compression artifacts, occlusion, or perspective distortion. Robust evaluation under these conditions, including degradation curves across corruption severity levels, remains an important direction for future work. Prediction uncertainty quantification and interpretability tools such as Grad-CAM and SHAP are logical next steps, as understanding which image regions and features drive model decisions is a reasonable expectation before deployment in any safety-critical setting.

Supplementary Material:

Additional details including pseudocode, experimental setup, detection results, gate distribution analysis, temperature sensitivity, and ablation study are provided in the supplementary document (Sections S1–S6)

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